

Solar Power at Scale: Quantifying Land Use Change Across China from 2010 to 2024

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Summary

Rapid growth of renewable energy is required to meet Net Zero targets around the world. Solar photovoltaics are expected to dominate, requiring notable land use change, especially in China, where growth has been greater than all other nations combined. A comprehensive assessment of land use change for solar power is necessary to evaluate ecological impacts and inform future energy planning. This study combines solar power and landcover datasets to quantify long-term changes in the spatial distribution and landcover types of solar power plants in China from 2010 to 2024. The total area for solar power over this period increased from 6.6 km² to 5584.6 km². The previous landcover type varied significantly among regions, with most solar built on impervious surfaces in East China, grasslands in the North and Southwest, and barren land in the Northwest. This study provides the first national-scale spatio-temporal assessment of land used for solar power across China and provides a critical foundation for quantifying the implications, both positive and negative, of solar power development.

KEYWORDS: Solar power plant; Land cover; Spatial and temporal change

1. Introduction

Solar power is a type of renewable energy characterised by relatively low cost, a readily accessible resource, and continuous technological advancement. Solar power facilities provide

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robust support for global energy transition (Chen et al. 2024). In recent years, nations worldwide have extended various policy incentives to solar power, continually expanding its capacity. Solar power has been the fastest-growing renewable energy type globally (IRENA 2025), however, with capacity expanding, the low energy density of solar power generates substantial land requirements (Blaydes et al. 2025).

The large amount of land required for solar developments presents a trade-off with the ecosystem services originally provided by previous landcover types (Hernandez et al. 2019). Outcomes can be both positive, for example, co-use of land with agriculture (Widmer et al. 2024), or negative, for example, if built on natural land, solar power can impact landscape connectivity, habitats, and biodiversity (Levin et al. 2023). To maximise positive and minimise negative synergies with sustainable development goals, measuring, regulating, and limiting land occupation for solar power is a necessary measure. This requires a comprehensive analysis of land occupied by solar power.

In recent years, policy preferences regarding land used by solar power in China have evolved with capacity increases. In addition, solar radiation resources vary substantially across China, with higher potential concentrated in arid and semi-arid regions in the northwest, which further shapes the spatial distribution of solar power plants. Several researchers have published datasets on the geospatial extent of solar installations over time. Moreover, annual landcover data enable landcover types used by solar to be quantified. Thus, the aims of this study are: (i) to quantify the increasing area of solar power plants in time and space; and (ii) to quantify the types of landcover used by solar. The results of this study could inform future placement of solar power plants in the landscape and their likely ecological impacts.

2. Study area and Materials

2.1. Study area

China ranks first in both growth and capacity of solar power among countries worldwide. By the end of 2024, China accounted for 48.3% of global installed solar capacity (901.7 GW) (IRENA 2025). China is a vast territory with highly diverse landscapes, containing 345 cities in 34 province-level administrative units and 7 geographical regions (**Figure 1**). The extensive and rapid construction of solar power plants makes comprehensive city-level and region-level measurement urgent.

Figure 1 Cities, provinces, and geographical regions of China.

2.2. Data and Method

The locations of solar power plants were compiled from published articles. Chen et al (2024) produced a dataset for China with installation dates for 2010–2022. Zeng et al (2025) generated a global dataset for 2019–2025. Combining the datasets of Chen et al (2024) for 2010–2022 and from Zeng et al (2025) for 2023–2024, we were able to quantify land taken by solar power over the period 2010 to 2024.

The China landcover dataset produced by Yang et al. (2021) at a spatial resolution of 30 m was used to calculate the area and landcover types occupied by solar power. Because large-scale installation of solar power in China began in 2010, we used landcover data for 2010 to assess the landcover types on which solar power plants were built each year thereafter.

Construction years of solar power plants were obtained from original solar power datasets. Spatial and statistical analyses were conducted using ArcGIS Pro (3.4.3). The “Zonal Statistics as Table” tool was used to summarize underlying landcover types and cities in which solar power plants were located. Individual data were subsequently aggregated to city-level and region-level for reporting purposes.

3. Results

3.1. Temporal changes and spatial distribution of solar power plants

Compared with Liu et al. (2024), our estimate of solar power plant area in 2020 (2970 km²) differed by only 4.3% from their reported value (2847 km²), indicating strong consistency.

From 2010 to 2024, the total area of solar power plants in China expanded dramatically, from 6.6 km² to 5584.6 km², an area 3.6 times the size of Greater London (**Figure 2**). Northwest region contained the largest area of solar power plants among all regions, and witnessed the greatest growth from 2022 (1483 km²) to 2023 (2346 km²). Since 2014, North China has ranked second in terms of solar power area. In 2012, total solar power plant area in any city did not exceed 40 km². In 2016, northern cities possessed larger solar areas than southern cities, and in 2020, solar areas increased in both northern and southern cities. The number of cities with solar power plant areas exceeding 100 km² (roughly the size of metropolitan Paris) rose from three in 2020 to twelve in 2024.

a. Solar power plant area of China and seven geographical regions from 2010 to 2024

Figure 2 Solar power plant area. (a) Temporal changes from 2010 to 2024. (b-e) Spatial distribution of solar power plant area across cities in 2012, 2016, 2020, and 2024.

3.2. Changes in landcover types

Among all landcover types, solar power plants were mostly built upon cropland, grassland, and

barren land, which together accounted for over 85% of the total area (**Figure 3**). From 2010 to 2022, grassland and cropland dominated solar land occupation, whereas installations upon barren land increased sharply in 2023, making it the dominant landcover type in 2024 (1698.8 km²). Distinct spatial patterns of solar power plants on different landcover types were observed. Solar power plants were mostly constructed on cropland in eastern cities and grassland in North China and Southwest region. Solar power plants were mostly constructed on barren land in the Northwest region, with the individual plant size larger than those on cropland, grassland, or impervious surfaces. Installations on impervious surfaces were most commonly located in East China, especially in coastal cities.

Figure 3 Landcover types occupied by solar power plants in China. (a) Temporal changes from 2010 to 2024. (b) Proportion of solar power plant area across different landcover types. Solar power plant area on cropland (c), grassland (d), barren (e), and impervious surfaces (f) in 2024.

4. Discussion

The temporal and spatial expansion of solar power plants reflects both the cost reduction in photovoltaics as the technology has matured, and a response to policies that influence its deployment. For example, the proportion of solar power plants built on cropland and water

bodies decreased in 2024. This was in response to the Ministry of Natural Resources, in 2021, beginning to restrict the conversion of general cropland to other uses and the Ministry of Water Resources, in 2022, prohibited the construction of solar projects on rivers, lakes, and reservoirs. Furthermore, in 2023, the National Forestry and Grassland Administration (2023) specified forest types where solar projects were permitted or prohibited, to better protect forest land and avoid ecological impacts. Moreover, the encouragement from the National Development and Reform Commission and Administration in 2021 promoted solar deployment in deserts and bare land, leading to an increase in installations on barren land after 2023.

5. Conclusion

This study provides valuable insight on the temporal and spatial expansion of solar power plants in China. It evidences the importance of policy on the distribution of solar power plants and types of landcover change. The findings also provide the start point for future research on the ecological impacts of solar power plant installations across different landscapes, including the potential implications for landscape connectivity, habitats, and biodiversity, all of which are critical for ecosystem function.

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References

- Blaydes H., Whyatt J.D., Carvalho F., Lee H.K., McCann K., et al (2025). Shedding light on land use change for solar farms. *Progress in Energy*, 7, 033001.
- Chen Y.H., Zhou J.Y., Ge Y., Dong J.W. (2024). Uncovering the rapid expansion of photovoltaic power plants in China from 2010 to 2022 using satellite data and deep learning. *Remote Sensing of Environment*, 305, 114100.
- Ministry of Water Resources of the People's Republic of China (2022). Guiding Opinions on Strengthening the Spatial Control of River and Lake Shorelines. https://www.gov.cn/gongbao/content/2022/content_5701574.htm.
- Hernandez R.R., Armstrong A., Burney J., Ryan G., Moore-O'Leary K., et al (2019). Techno-ecological synergies of solar energy for global sustainability. *Nature Sustainability*, 2, 560-568.
- IRENA (2025). Renewable energy statistics 2025. https://www.irena.org/-/media/Files/IRENA/Agency/Publication/2025/Jul/IRENA_DAT_RE_Statistics_2025.pdf.
- Levin M.O., Kalies E.L., Forester E., Jackson E.L.A., Levin A.H., et al (2023). Solar Energy-driven Land-cover Change Could Alter Landscapes Critical to Animal Movement in the Continental United States. *Environmental Science & Technology*, 57, 11499-11509.
- Liu J., Wang J.Y., Li L.H. (2024). Vectorized solar photovoltaic installation dataset across China in 2015 and 2020. *Scientific Data*, 11, 1446.
- Ministry of Natural Resources of the People's Republic of China, et al (2021). Notice on Issues Related to Strict Cropland Use Control. https://www.gov.cn/zhengce/zhengceku/2021-12/26/content_5664643.htm
- Ministry of Natural Resources of the People's Republic of China, et al (2023). Notice on Supporting the Development of Photovoltaic Power Generation Industry and Standardizing Land Management. <https://www.gov.cn/zhengce/zhengceku/2023->

04/03/content_5749824.htm

National Development and Reform Commission, et al (2021). Notice on the List of the First Batch of Large scale Wind and Photovoltaic Base Construction Projects Focusing on Desert, Gobi, and Desert Areas.

Widmer J., Christ B., Grenz J., Norgrove L. (2024). Agrivoltaics, a promising new tool for electricity and food production: A systematic review. *Renewable and Sustainable Energy Reviews*, 192, 114277.

Yang J., Huang X. (2021). The 30 m annual land cover dataset and its dynamics in China from 1990 to 2019. *Earth System Science Data*, 13, 3907-3925.

Zeng X., Sun W., Jia M., Xue Z., Zhou C., et al (2025). Global high-resolution mapping of photovoltaic power plants from 2019 to 2025 using unsupervised index-based multi-source data fusion method. *International Journal of Applied Earth Observation and Geoinformation*, 145, 105005.

Biographies

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